

Effect of Mn doping on conductivity and Photocatalytic behaviour of SmFeO_3

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Abstract

Ferrites and orthoferrites have attracted research interest as an eco-friendly material to substitute toxic lead based perovskites in various applications (1). The Mn doped SmFeO_3 (SFO) were prepared by facile sol-gel method which shows distorted type of structure in the space group Pbnm (2). The AC conductivity has been measured which shows an increasing tendency with the temperature, indicates the semiconducting behaviour of the material. Hence, a semiconductor to metallic transition at the temperature 723 K has also been found. The visible light induced photocatalytic tests were performed by the degradation of organic pollutant Rh-B and the result reflects that the apparent rate constant (K) has been increased with higher amount of Mn concentration. Additionally, higher Mn doping causes decrease in band gap from 2.60 eV to 1.82 eV. The enhanced photocatalytic activity and conductivity of the material may happen due to Mn doping which enhance the active catalytic sites.

Fig : (a) The AC conductivity at room temperature and (b) the Photocatalytic degradation of RhB as a function of the irradiation time under visible light for the as-prepared Mn-doped SFO samples.

References:

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